

Critical Discourse Analysis on Public Relations and Promotion of Safe School Initiative in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study was carried out to examine the relationship between public relations strategies and the promotion of safe school initiatives in Nigeria. Anchored on stakeholder theory and supported by excellence theory of public relations, the researchers adopted a library research method and critical discourse analysis to analyse the data. The findings revealed that public relations strategies are crucial for managing insecurity, enhancing security measures and promoting safe school environments in Nigeria. Various strategies, including press releases, social media, community awareness programmes and reputation management, are employed in Nigerian educational institutions to achieve safe school objectives. The study also showed that public relations strategies can enhance communication efficiency, productivity, conflict resolution and public acceptance, indicating potential effectiveness in promoting safe school initiatives. However, challenges such as inadequate resources, lack of trained personnel, poor communication, corruption, insecurity and management interference hinder the effectiveness of public relations strategies. The study concluded that public relations is essential in managing safe school initiatives, but ineffective use and challenges can limit the achievement of desired results. To address these challenges, the study, among other things, recommended developing comprehensive public relations plans and utilising social media for safety awareness.

Keywords: Public Relations, Safe School Initiative, Critical Discourse Analysis

Introduction

The need to relate favourably with various publics continues to be a cardinal goal of every organisation or institution globally. To succeed in doing so, public relations becomes vital anchor that keeps reputation and relationships between organisations and their publics afloat (Aja, Chukwu & Odoh, 2019; Orji-Egwu & Nworie, 2023; Oyeleke, Ude, Ewa-Ibe & Nwamini, 2018; Shimawua & Kusugh, 2024) and the practice cuts across every field of human endeavour, be it politics, economy, governance, management and education to mention but a few (Dornyoy & Adiku, 2015; Ikenna, 2022; John & Idi, 2021; Nwambuko, 2017). As a result, public relations practice comprises a wide range of activities with varying purposes that aim to assist organisations in developing and sustaining the variety of relationships that ensure their long-term success. It encourages

increased productivity, corporate discipline and a peaceful industrial ecology, as well as persuades people of an individual's, institution's or organisation's credibility, performance, potentials and the quality of its offered products or services. Furthermore, public relations provide benefits such as developing good relationships with both internal and external publics, as well as increasing brand awareness (Muhammad & Adamkolo, 2018; Obinna, Ewomazina & Olley, 2021; Udofot & Sambe, 2021).

Due to its significance in modern organisations, educational institutions are also engaged in the use of public relations tool to achieve their operational goals. It is to be noted that institutional institutions have adopted professional public relations practice owing to rapid expansion of its stakeholders, increase in staff and students population and the complex social issues that they grapple with. Owing to expansion in staff and students population, communication effectiveness and efficiency has also become a formidable task for most tertiary institutions (Aikins & Adu-Oppong, 2015; Nwafor, Omoevah & Umuze, 2022; Olaoluwa, 2021; Omorodion, Ibeneme & Ayodele, 2022; Orji-Egwu & Nworie, 2023).

If tertiary institutions are adopting public relations tools in the management of their affairs, studying to establish with Safe School Initiative as relates to promotion of the programme remains very crucial (Shimawua & Kusugh, 2022). This is in view of the increase in the incidences of school attacks, resulting to destruction of school infrastructure, abduction of teachers and students, closure of schools and increase in internal displacement of persons in affected areas prone to security threats (NILDS, 2021; Uzuegbu-Wilson, 2023).

Public Relations and Public Relations Strategies

The concept of public relations has been defined in various ways, with scholars emphasising different aspects of the field. Okafor & Nwatu (2018) note the lack of consensus on a definition, while Orakwue, Hammond & Gyambrah-Adaefie (2021) highlight the evolution of definitions from press agency-focused to more comprehensive approaches incorporating research, planning, evaluation, and relationship-building.

Public relations is considered a management function that establishes and maintains mutual relationships and communications between organisations and their publics and stakeholders (Ugoji, Idibia & Thomas, 2022). It acts as a bridge builder, fostering understanding and interest between organisations and their publics (Ugoji, Idibia & Thomas, 2022). Effective public relations involves planned actions, evaluation and long-term commitment (Oshie & Ushie, 2021; Cutlip *et al* 2005). In the context of promoting safe school initiatives in Nigeria, public relations strategies can play a crucial role in building trust and understanding between schools, stakeholders and the public. By employing effective planning, research, and evaluation, public relations can help achieve organisational goals (Oshie & Ushie, 2021). The complexity of public relations, with various areas of specialisation (Daramola, 2003 in Adedokun, Oke & Olagoke, 2023), highlights the need for a nuanced approach to promoting safe school initiatives.

Based on the synthesis of previous scholars' views, a new definition of public relations in the context of promoting safe school initiatives in Nigeria could be: Public

relations is a strategic management function that establishes and maintains mutually beneficial relationships between organisations and their publics through deliberate, planned, and sustained efforts, fostering understanding, trust and cooperation to achieve organisational goals and promote social responsibility. This definition incorporates key elements from previous definitions, including relationship-building, strategic planning and mutual understanding. In the context of promoting safe school initiatives in Nigeria, this definition highlights the importance of public relations in building trust and cooperation between schools, stakeholders, and the public.

Safe-School Initiative Programme

The Safe School Initiative programme represents a crucial intervention aimed at ensuring a secure and protective educational atmosphere for students, educators, and school administrators in Nigeria, with a particular focus on the North-East region. As noted by Manjo (2024), Niyi, Evans & Adebayo (2024), along with Their World (2018), this initiative emerged from collaborative efforts to establish safe schools and conducive learning environments during periods of conflict and emergencies. The programme encompasses a blend of school-based interventions, community-based initiatives, and specific protective measures for vulnerable populations (Niyi, Evans & Adebayo, 2024).

Academics concur that the Safe School Initiative programme is intended to tackle the issue of insecurity within educational institutions throughout Nigeria, particularly in the North-East region (Niyi, Evans & Adebayo, 2024; Manjo, 2024). The programme's objective is to shield students from violence, bullying, harassment, kidnapping, and exposure to weapons and threats, thus ensuring a tranquil environment conducive to teaching and learning (Chester, 2015; NMS, 2021). The advantages of the Safe School Initiative programme are extensive, including the establishment of a secure school environment, the seamless execution of educational services, a decrease in educational wastage, and the enhancement of students' academic performance and outcomes (Niyi, Evans & Adebayo, 2024). Nevertheless, the programme encounters obstacles such as insufficient funding, corruption, inadequate monitoring and evaluation, and limited stakeholder engagement (Niyi, Evans & Adebayo, 2024).

Based on the synthesis of previous scholars' views, a new definition of Safe School Initiative programme can be proposed as: A comprehensive and collaborative programme designed to provide a safe, protective and sustainable learning environment for students, teachers, and school administrators in conflict-prone areas, thereby promoting the smooth implementation of teaching and learning, reducing educational wastage and guaranteeing academic achievement and outcome. This definition captures the essence of the Safe School Initiative programme as a vital intervention aimed at ensuring the safety and well-being of students, teachers and school administrators in Nigeria, particularly in the North-East region.

Need for Public Relations Strategies in the Promotion of Safe-School Initiative in Nigeria

The Safe School Initiative program represents a crucial response to the security issues confronting Nigeria's educational sector, especially in the North-East region. Experts concur that the programme's objective is to improve human security within schools by

establishing community security groups, advocating for safe educational zones, and ensuring the long-term physical safeguarding of schools (Gever, 2016; *Daily Sun editorial*, 2014). The core purpose of the programme is to guarantee that students, educators, and school administrators can perform their daily functions without the threat of violence, kidnapping or intimidation (Ayeni & Beji, 2018).

The importance of public relations strategies in advancing the Safe School Initiative programme cannot be overstated. Public relations is essential in cultivating and maintaining relationships between organisations and their varied audiences (Nwokoye, 2008; Chukwu, as cited in Orakwue, Hammond & Gyambrah-Adaefie, 2021). Effective public relations can encourage dialogue, enhance understanding, and establish trust among stakeholders (Maiwada *et al* 2025). Scholars characterise public relations as a management function that creates and sustains mutually advantageous relationships between an organisation and its audiences (Cutlip, Center & Broom, 2006). Public relations strategies can effectively promote the Safe School Initiative programme by raising awareness, establishing trust, and encouraging dialogue among stakeholders. Various public relations tools can be employed, including media relations, advertorials, social media, newsletters, community relations, and sponsorship (Igben, 2022; Orakwue, Hammond & Gyambrah-Adaefie, 2021). By utilising these tools, the Safe School Initiative programme can cultivate a favorable image, advance its objectives and ultimately fulfill its goals.

The existing literature indicates that public relations plays a crucial role in peacebuilding and fostering sustainable development in Nigeria (Maiwada *et al* 2025). Through the implementation of inclusive, transparent, and ethical strategies, public relations can greatly aid in creating a harmonious and secure atmosphere for students, educators and school administrators.

Use of Public Relations Strategies in the Promotion of Safe School Initiative in Nigeria

The implementation of public relations strategies is crucial for the promotion of the Safe School Initiative programme in Nigeria. Public relations serves to provide an institution or individuals with visibility to their audiences through matters of public interest and news that does not necessitate direct payment (Ejiogu, Clinton-Ogu & Uwalaka, 2024; Ivy Panda, 2023). Researchers concur that public relations can facilitate communication among employees, customers, voters, or the general public (Ejiogu, Clinton-Ogu & Uwalaka, 2024).

Establishing effective public relations necessitates the utilisation of suitable tools, which include publicity, public relations advertising, and special events (Chukwu, 2012). Publicity, as a mass communication tool, can be characterised as the creation of news regarding a person, product, or service that is featured in broadcast or print media (Doug and Hanson, 2003). Various methods can be employed to achieve publicity, such as news releases, service feature articles, product publicity, financial publicity, photography and printed materials (Chukwu, 2012).

Organisations may also leverage event sponsorship, scholarships and sports to fulfill objectives such as publicity, marketing, entertainment, and social responsibility. Facility tours can be arranged for members of the public to improve the organisation's image (Ugbaja, 2014). In educational institutions, public relations is utilised to oversee the flow of both internal and external communication, fostering two-way communication based on research through multimedia (Sietel, 2009). The responsibilities of public relations practitioners have expanded to encompass leadership roles, including publicising, advertising, marketing, editing and crisis management (Flat, 2002).

The corporate image holds significant value and is susceptible to damage; therefore, cultivating positive relationships with students, employees, and the media is essential for garnering favourable publicity, enhancing corporate reputation and mitigating negative rumours and stock fluctuations (Clow & Baack, 2007; Kotler, 2003). Implementing effective public relations strategies can facilitate the promotion of the Safe School Initiative programme, establish trust and encourage dialogue among stakeholders.

Effectiveness of Public Relations Strategies in the Promotion and Implementation of Safe-School Initiative in Nigeria

Public relations plays a vital role in organisational reputation management and external relationships, serving as a shield that minimises risk and damage while promoting growth and evolution (Orji-Egwu & Nworie, 2023). Effective public relations campaigns enhance brand recognition, relevance and employee impact (Awosemusi & Awofadeju, 2023; Szilagyi, 2011). In educational institutions, public relations strategies aid in interpreting public attitudes, shaping policies and maintaining a favourable image (Obinna, Ewomazina & Olley, 2021; Wherry, 1982). Public relations also facilitates international academic collaborations, global exposure and crisis management (Business Standard, 2020).

Challenges in the use of Public Relations Strategies for Promotion of Safe-School Initiative in Nigeria

However, the practice of public relations in Nigeria faces challenges, including corruption, lack of academic exposition, career determination, finance, personnel and government support (Aja, Chukwu & Odoh, 2019). Other pitfalls include convincing staff and teachers, cost, lip service, audience neglect and inadequate technological skills (Ugoji, Idibia & Thomas, 2022). Despite these challenges, public relations has the potential to influence decision-making, conflict resolution, and agenda building (Mojaye & Aondover, 2022; Grunig & Stamm, 2003).

The effectiveness of public relations strategies in promoting and implementing safe-school initiatives in Nigeria depends on addressing these challenges and leveraging the strengths of public relations in educational institutions. By understanding the role of public relations in shaping public attitudes, managing crises and fostering international collaborations, educational institutions can develop effective strategies to promote safe-school initiatives.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on stakeholder theory and excellence theory. The stakeholder theory and excellence theory offer essential frameworks for comprehending public relations strategies aimed at advancing safe school initiatives. The stakeholder theory underscores the importance of fostering positive relationships with a variety of stakeholders through continuous dialogue, collaboration and partnership (Ebere & Okon, 2023). This theory accentuates the necessity of transparent and ethical communication practices to cultivate trust, credibility and sustained support for safe school initiatives. Nevertheless, its successful application necessitates recognising practical challenges and potential limitations related to balancing the interests of diverse stakeholders.

The excellence theory, introduced by James Grunig, asserts that organisations can achieve greater effectiveness through the implementation of public relations strategies (Ebere & Okon, 2023; Grunig, 2003). This theory delineates the attributes of effective public relations, which include the robust empowerment of the public relations function, the roles of communicators, the organisation of communication functions and various public relations models. Notably, the two-way symmetrical model is particularly pertinent, as it emphasises both internal and external communication and the cultivation of relationships.

Both theories align on the critical role of effective communication, stakeholder engagement and strategic planning within public relations. By leveraging these theories, educational institutions can formulate impactful public relations strategies to advocate for safe school initiatives, foster trust and credibility with stakeholders and ultimately realise their objectives.

Methodology

The researchers employed library research method wherein data were gathered from various sources, including books, journals, book chapters, newspapers, magazines and the internet. Online research citation engines such as Google, Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Web of Science and Academia were utilised to facilitate access to pertinent materials.

Discussion

Empirical research underscores the necessity of public relations strategies for advancing safe school initiatives in Nigeria. Research emphasises the significance of engaging stakeholders, fostering community relations and managing crises to address insecurity and improve security measures (Shimawua & Kusugh, 2022; Shimawua & Kusugh, 2024; John & Idi, 2021). Public relations strategies can take various forms, encompassing community relations, corporate social responsibility, and ongoing communication (John & Idi, 2021). Nevertheless, obstacles such as inadequate funding and insecurity demand the implementation of effective public relations strategies (Niyi, Evans & Adebayo, 2024). Additionally, studies highlight the contribution of security agencies in advocating for school safety, emphasising the necessity of public relations strategies to bolster security measures (Uzuegbu-Wilson, 2023). The critical nature of robust relationships between authorities and the public, as indicated in police-public relations research, can be

applied to safe-school initiatives (Zems, 2016). In summary, empirical evidence indicates that public relations strategies are vital for fostering safe school environments in Nigeria, necessitating effective stakeholder engagement, community relations and crisis management.

Empirical studies highlight various public relations strategies used in Nigerian educational institutions to achieve objectives and promote safe school initiatives. These strategies include press releases, social media, community awareness programmes, open talk-shows and reputation management (Nwafor, Omoevah & Umuze, 2022; Omorodion, Ibeneme & Ayodele, 2022; Okafor & Nwatu, 2018). Public relations practices such as attending to users' enquiries and providing suggestion boxes are also used for effective service delivery (Ogboniyomi, 2024). Additionally, strategies like dialogue, mediation and community relations can be applied to safe-school initiatives, as identified in peace-building efforts during political activities (Kalu, Igyuve & Akase, 2024). These studies demonstrate the versatility and effectiveness of public relations strategies in Nigerian educational institutions, including managing crises, improving service delivery and promoting educational programmes. By adopting similar strategies, educational institutions can promote safe school initiatives and achieve their objectives.

Empirical studies demonstrate the effectiveness of public relations strategies in various contexts, suggesting potential applicability to promoting safe-school initiatives in Nigeria. Research findings indicate that public relations strategies can enhance communication efficiency, increase productivity, resolve conflicts and influence public acceptance (Emike, Akase & Ogande, 2024; Ejiogu, Clinton-Ogu & Uwalaka, 2024; Iyadi & Okolie, 2017). Additionally, studies have shown that public relations management practices can positively impact business performance and organisational perception (Mpuon *et al* 2023; Ewurum *et al* 2024). These findings suggest that public relations strategies can be effective in promoting safe-school initiatives by enhancing communication, resolving conflicts, and influencing public acceptance. By adopting effective public relations strategies, educational institutions can potentially improve safety and security in schools.

Empirical studies highlight various challenges facing the use of public relations strategies in Nigeria, which can hinder the effectiveness of programmes aimed at promoting safe school initiatives. These challenges include inadequate resources, lack of trained personnel, poor communication, corruption, insecurity, management interference and inadequate involvement in decision-making (Aikins & Adu-Oppong, 2015; Awosemusi & Awofadeju, 2023; Ewurum *et al* 2024; Niyi, Evans & Adebayo, 2024; Orji-Egwu & Nworie, 2023; Shimawua & Kusugh, 2024). Additionally, funding shortages, lack of professionals and ungoverned spaces can also impact the effectiveness of public relations strategies in promoting safe school initiatives (Niyi, Evans & Adebayo, 2024; Udofot & Sambe, 2021; Uzuegbu-Wilson, 2023). These challenges can affect the ethical practice of public relations, requiring urgent attention for success (Olaoluwa, 2021). Addressing these challenges is crucial to ensuring the effectiveness of public relations strategies in promoting safe school initiatives in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Nigeria is currently facing a number of security challenges which institutions of learning are badly affected and public relations is recognised as essential for managing insecurity, enhancing security measures, and promoting safe school environments in Nigeria. As a result, various public relations strategies are used in Nigerian educational institutions, including press releases, social media, community awareness programs, open talk-shows, and reputation management, to achieve objectives and promote safe school initiatives. Consequently, these public relations strategies have been found to be effective in enhancing communication efficiency, increasing productivity, resolving conflicts, and influencing public acceptance, suggesting potential effectiveness in promoting safe-school initiatives in Nigeria. However, there are challenges facing the use of public relations strategies in Nigeria include inadequate resources, lack of trained personnel, poor communication, corruption, insecurity, and management interference, which can hinder the effectiveness of programmes aimed at promoting safe school initiatives if not addressed. Finally, public relations is essential in the management of safe-school initiative but ineffective use and many other challenges can hinder the effectiveness of the practice and limits the level if not at all prevent the achievement of the desired results. Thus, there is need to develop a comprehensive public relations plan to manage insecurity and promote safe school environments in Nigerian educational institutions. Also, there is need to utilise social media platforms to disseminate safety tips and awareness campaigns to students, parents and staff in real-time.

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